

Validation of HNO₃ spectroscopic parameters using atmospheric absorption and emission measurements.

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Abstract:

The improved database of HNO₃ spectroscopic parameters in the 600-950 cm⁻¹ spectral region presented in [Gomez L, Tran H, Perrin A, Gamache RR, Laraia A, Orphal J, Chélin P, Fellows CE, Hartmann JM, JQSRT, submitted, 2008] is tested by comparisons between calculations and atmospheric remotely sensed absorption and emission spectra. The line parameters in the 11.3 μm region are validated using ground-based Fourier transform solar absorption measurements, whereas those in the 13.1 μm region are successfully tested using balloon-borne atmospheric emission spectra. In both regions, the quality of the line parameters and the consistency between band intensities is confirmed through comparisons with emission spectra collected by the satellite-borne MIPAS instrument.

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1. Introduction

Nitric acid is a trace gas playing an important role in stratospheric chemistry. In the stratosphere, HNO_3 is a reservoir molecule which links the (NO_x) , and (HO_x) chemical families, since it is formed in the following three-body process:

The dominant loss processes are the photolysis of HNO_3 and the reaction with OH, *ie*:

The solid nitric acid trihydrate aerosols (NAT) were recently identified to be key participants to the efficient night time conversion, in polar stratospheric clouds, of the inactive chlorine species HCl and ClONO_2 to the potentially photochemically active Cl_2 and HOCl. As the NAT aerosols are soluble in water, the net result of these chemical processes is a global denitrification in the polar region, a condition which facilitates the springtime destruction of ozone by active chlorine.

Infrared remote sensing techniques are routinely used to determine volume mixing ratio (vmr) profiles of HNO_3 in the atmosphere. For such retrievals, the $11.3 \mu\text{m}$ region is one of the most widely used, starting from spectra recorded by ground-based [1-3], balloon-borne [4-6] and space-borne spectrometers [7-16]. This spectral region is of particular interest since it contains the strong ν_5 and $2\nu_9$ bands and, being centered in an atmospheric window, it is practically free of interfering contributions by other species. Due to their importance for remote sensing, HNO_3 spectra near $11.3 \mu\text{m}$ have been the subject of numerous laboratory spectroscopic studies (see [17] and references therein).

In our preceding paper [17], some of the HNO_3 spectroscopic parameters in the $600\text{-}950 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ spectral range have been improved with respect to the very recently updated edition of the HITRAN database [18]. Firstly, line parameters were added for the $\nu_5+\nu_6-\nu_6$ and $\nu_5+\nu_7-\nu_7$ hot bands, centered at 869.1 and 875.7 cm^{-1} , respectively. The second improvement concerns the air broadening coefficients and their temperature dependence for which semi-classical calculations were performed [19]. These transition dependent data then replaced the former values which were obtained [20] from an approximate extrapolation of a few existing measurements. Finally, a model was proposed in order to account for line-mixing effects within the Q branch of the $\nu_5+\nu_9-\nu_9$ hot band at 885.4 cm^{-1} . In addition to these modifications, the line intensities of the ν_6 and ν_8 bands (centered at 646.8 and 763.1 cm^{-1} , respectively) were improved. All these modifications, which were tested and validated using laboratory measurements, are described in detail in Ref. [17].

The present paper extends the test of the improved database by making comparisons between calculations and atmospheric absorption and emission spectra measured by various

instruments. The changes performed in the 11.3 μm region are validated using ground-based Fourier transform solar absorption measurements, whereas those near 13.1 μm are successfully tested using balloon-borne atmospheric emission spectra. Finally, the quality of the new database and the consistency between band intensities in both regions are confirmed through comparisons with emission spectra collected by the satellite-borne MIPAS instrument.

2. Atmospheric spectra

Ground based solar absorption measurements were made in Kiruna (Sweden), early 2003, by the IMK group, using the high resolution Fourier transform spectrometer described in Ref. [21]. Four of the spectra have been used in the present study, obtained for apparent solar elevation angles of 2.6°, 4.2°, 14.6° and 27.4°, respectively. They are calibrated to absolute radiance units and the atmospheric transmission for each recording is thus obtained by dividing the measured radiances by the extraterrestrial solar value.

In the Smithsonian Astrophysical Observatory (SAO) experiment [22] a balloon-borne Fourier transform instrument is used. The limb viewing emission data analyzed thereafter were obtained on 30 April 1997 over Alaska. They consist of nine radiance spectra in the 325-917 cm^{-1} spectral range recorded at float (balloon at 40 km) for tangent heights from about 37 down to 10 km.

The Michelson Interferometer for Passive Atmospheric Sounding (MIPAS) experiment [23] is a spectrometer onboard the ENVISAT satellite. The MIPAS limb emission radiances used in this work are the same as those used in Ref. [16]. They were selected among the observations acquired during the “well-characterized” ENVISAT orbits 2081 and 2082 (July 2002), with nominal tangent altitudes of 12 and 24 km.

The species which provide the principal absorption lines in the considered spectral region are H_2O , CO_2 , O_3 , N_2O , CH_4 , and HNO_3 . The altitude distributions of their mixing ratios were deduced previously by the groups in charge of the instruments and, unless specified, are fixed in the present work. Similarly, the temperature and pressure profiles, the pointing geometry and the instrument response function, were determined independently and left unchanged in the calculations presented in the following section. Finally, aerosols and clouds are absent in all measurements used in this work and, in our calculations, only clear sky cases are thus considered.

3. Validation of the new database

3.1 Ground-based Fourier transform solar absorptions

Neglecting diffusion and latitudinal and longitudinal inhomogeneities, the atmospheric transmission $\tau(\sigma)$ at wavenumber σ is computed from:

$$\tau(\sigma) = \int F_{Instr}(\sigma - \sigma') d\sigma' \times \exp \left[- \int_{z_{Inst}}^{z_{Max}} \sum_a \alpha_a[\sigma', x_a, T(z), p(z)] \frac{ds}{dz}(z) dz \right], \quad (1)$$

where F_{Instr} is the area-normalized instrument function and the integration over altitude (z) is made along a curvilinear abscissa $s(z)$ following the line of sight. Note that the influence of the very narrow field of view is disregarded in Eq. (1). The sum is over all species “ a ” of significant contribution to absorption at wavenumber σ' . For a given absorbing molecule a , with mixing ratio x_a under total pressure p at temperature T , the local value of the absorption coefficient α_a is given by:

$$\alpha_a(\sigma, x_a, T, p) = x_a p \times \sigma \left[1 - \exp \left(- \frac{hc\sigma}{k_B T} \right) \right] \left\{ \sum_{\ell_a} \frac{S_{\ell_a}(T)}{\sigma_{\ell_a} [1 - \exp(-hc\sigma_{\ell_a}/kT)]} \times \frac{1}{\gamma_a^D(\sigma_{\ell_a}, T)} \sqrt{\frac{\ln 2}{\pi}} \times \text{Re} \left[W \left(\frac{\sigma - \sigma_{\ell_a} - p\delta_{\ell_a}}{\gamma_a^D(\sigma_{\ell_a}, T)/\sqrt{\ln 2}} + i \frac{p\gamma_{\ell_a}(T)}{\gamma_a^D(\sigma_{\ell_a}, T)/\sqrt{\ln 2}} \right) \right] \right\}, \quad (2)$$

where the sum extends over the absorption lines ℓ_a of species “ a ”. The quantities γ_a^D , σ_{ℓ_a} , γ_{ℓ_a} , δ_{ℓ_a} , S_{ℓ_a} are the Doppler width (cm^{-1}), the unperturbed line position (cm^{-1}), the line broadening and shifting coefficients ($\text{cm}^{-1}/\text{atm}$) and the integrated intensity ($\text{cm}^{-2}/\text{atm}$). $W(x,y)$ is the complex probability function [24,25], and $\text{Re}[\dots]$ denotes the real part which leads to the (assumed) Voigt profile.

Note that the HNO_3 profile was originally deduced from these IMK spectra using the 2000 edition of the HITRAN database. Since the intensity of all lines of HNO_3 in the $820\text{-}950 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ region was decreased by about 11% from this edition to the version that we use here, the present calculations use HNO_3 amounts raised by 11%.

Comparisons between measured and calculated atmospheric transmissions for different spectral regions and two elevation angles are presented in Figs. 1-4. In all cases, calculations were performed using both the line parameter of the very last HITRAN database and the modified line list proposed in Ref. [17]. In order to focus on the improvement brought by the new database, only the spectral regions where modifications were made are displayed. In Figs. 1 and 2, we show the results obtained in the intervals where the $\nu_5+\nu_7-\nu_7$ and $\nu_5+\nu_6-\nu_6$ hot bands were added. These

regions are particularly important since they contain only HNO₃ transitions and are therefore often (partly) retained as micro-windows to retrieve the HNO₃ vmr [2,12,13]. As can be observed in Figs. 1-2, the new line list leads to significant improvements. This is confirmed, for another elevation angle (14.50°), in Fig. 3. Finally, a comparison between measurements and calculations using our new line list in the $\nu_5+\nu_9-\nu_9$ hot band is presented in Fig. 4. Recall that line-mixing effects within the Q branch of this band were detected and that a model was proposed in [17]. As shown in Fig. 4, line-mixing effects have a small but detectable influence on the atmospheric transmission, and the model of Ref. [17] leads to a better agreement with measurements.

3.2 SAO atmospheric emission spectra

The balloon-borne Fourier transform instrument of the SAO experiment measures atmospheric thermal emission in the 325-917 cm⁻¹ region. In this case, the quantity deduced from measurements is the radiance I, given by:

$$I(\sigma) = \int_{FOV} d\Omega \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} F_{Instr}(\sigma - \sigma') \times I^{Atm}(\sigma', d\Omega) d\sigma', \quad (3)$$

where the first integration is over the field of view (FOV) of the instrument and radiances are convolved by the normalized instrument function F_{Instr} . I^{Atm} are spectral values of the intensity emitted by the atmosphere. Assuming local thermodynamic equilibrium, the latter are given by

$$I^{Atm}(\sigma, d\Omega) = \int_{Z_{obs}}^{\infty} \left\{ \sum_a \alpha_a[\sigma, x_a(z'), T(z'), p(z')] \times I_0[\sigma, T(z')] \times \exp\left(- \sum_a \int_{Z_{obs}}^{z'} \alpha_a[\sigma, x_a(z), T(z), p(z)] \frac{ds}{dz}(z, d\Omega) dz \right) \times \frac{ds}{dz}(z', d\Omega) dz' \right\}, \quad (4)$$

where I_0 is the black body radiance, and the absorption coefficient α_a of species “a” is calculated from Eq.(2), excepted in the case of CO₂ for which calculations are performed accounting for line-mixing using the model of Ref. [26]. Note that, for H₂O, a continuum is added to the local values of the absorption coefficient. These self- and air-broadened contributions, which are significant at long wavelengths, have been calculated using the CKD 2.4 data and software by Clough *et al* [27]. This specific treatment for CO₂ and H₂O is required here since higher frequencies are considered. For HNO₃, the vmr profile was originally determined [28] from microwindows selected in the 22 μ m region using ν_9 band transitions with line intensities given in HITRAN [29], which were obtained through a scaling to the results of the ν_9 band intensity measurements performed in Ref. [30]. Since this time, Sirota *et al.* [31] have suggested a significantly weaker value (~28%) for the

ν_9 band intensity but this result was not validated by further measurements. Hence we have left the original HNO_3 profile unchanged.

Figures 5-6 present comparisons between measurements and calculations for the ν_8 region and various tangent heights. The present calculations were performed using both the HITRAN line list and our new database [17] in which ν_8 band line intensities were updated. As can be observed on these figures, a better agreement is obtained between the observed and calculated spectra when using the new parameters. On the other hand, when using HITRAN data, the calculations overestimate the emitted radiance in the 13.1 μm region lead. These results could indicate that there is a rather good consistency of the ν_8 (in [17]) and ν_9 [18,29] line intensities, while in HITRAN the (ν_8/ν_9) intensity ratio is about 20 % too strong.

3.3 MIPAS measurements

The new HNO_3 database has also been validated by comparing MIPAS measurements with spectra generated using alternatively the old [16,18] and the new [17] line parameters. This procedure was successfully adopted to validate MIPAS PF3.2 HNO_3 line parameters as described in Ref. [16], where technical details can be found. The MIPAS measurements used in the present study are the same as those used for the previous validation, *ie*: limb radiances selected among the observations acquired during orbits 2081 and 2082 (July 2002), for nominal tangent altitudes of 12 and 24 km. The corresponding simulations were calculated by using the two-dimensional forward model available at Bologna University. Three sets of synthetic spectra, in the 750-930 cm^{-1} spectral range (sub-interval of MIPAS band A), were generated using the two HNO_3 spectroscopic datasets and different vertical distribution profiles. The first set (labeled S1) uses the old spectroscopic database and HNO_3 vmr profiles retrieved by the MIPAS off-line processor operated with the same spectroscopic information. For the second set (S2), the same HNO_3 vmr profiles were used but with the new spectroscopic database [17]. In the third set of simulations (S3) both the new line list and HNO_3 vmr profiles retrieved with these new parameters were used. In all three cases, the retrieval of the HNO_3 vertical distributions was operated on the 876.375-879.375 cm^{-1} and 885.100-888.100 cm^{-1} spectral intervals. For each set of spectra, the differences between observed spectrum and the corresponding simulation were averaged and corrected using the Residual and Error Correlation analysis technique. The results of this analysis, presented in Table 1, clearly show that the new database leads to improved results in term of both average and root mean square (RMS) residuals. MIPAS measured spectra and differences with respect to calculated results obtained from limb radiance simulations of type S1, S2, and S3 are reported in Figures 7

and 8 for tangent heights of 12 and 24 km, respectively. These plots visually confirm the improvement achieved in both the 11 and 13 μm regions.

4. Conclusion

The results obtained in the present paper confirm the improvement brought by the new line list [17]. Furthermore, the comparisons between calculations and MIPAS and SAO spectra are in favor of an overall consistency of the intensities for the 13.1 μm (ν_8 band) to 11 μm ($\nu_5/2\nu_9$) regions, and for the 22 μm (ν_9) to 13.1 μm regions, respectively. They confirm the conclusion of the previous paper stating that the ν_8 band intensities in HITRAN [18] are too strong by $\sim 20\%$. It is clear, however, that future laboratory studies are needed in order to get more accurate information, in particular for the hot bands whose line positions and intensities are still not fully satisfactory ($\nu_5+\nu_9-\nu_9$, [10]) and were generated in a rather crude way ($\nu_5+\nu_6-\nu_6$, $\nu_5+\nu_7-\nu_7$) in our previous paper. Finally, additional laboratory line intensities are still needed for the 22 μm bands (ν_9 and corresponding hot bands) for which differing values as compared to those quoted on HITRAN were achieved in Ref. [31].

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Simulation type and database version	Tangent height of 12 km		Tangent height of 24 km	
	Average difference	RMS	Average difference	RMS
S1 - Old database	2.27	24.30	1.30	18.56
S3 - New database	-0.93	20.50	-0.22	16.09

Table 1: Characterization of the residuals obtained comparing MIPAS observed spectra with simulated spectra of type S1 and S3, for tangent height of 12 and 24 km. The results are in $\text{nW}/(\text{cm}^2 \text{ sr cm}^{-1})$.

Figure captions

Fig.1: Measured atmospheric transmission in the region of the $\nu_5+\nu_7-\nu_7$ for an elevation angle of 2.75° (●) and corresponding calculated values with (---) the old HNO₃ line list [16,18], and (—) the new improved one [17]. Plots in panels (a) and (b) are the corresponding differences between measured and calculated values. Panel (c) shows the difference between residuals reported in (a) and (b).

Fig. 2: Same as figure 1 but in the $\nu_5+\nu_6-\nu_6$ hot band region.

Fig. 3: Same as figure 1 but for an elevation angle of 14.50° .

Fig. 4: Same as figure 1 but for the $\nu_5+\nu_9-\nu_9$ hot band region.

Fig. 5: SAO radiances collected from 36.7 km for a tangent height of 20.0 km. The upper part gives measurement and values calculated using (---) line parameters given in HITRAN, and (—) line parameters of the improved list [17]. The curves in (a) and (b) are the corresponding measured-calculated deviations averaged over 0.01 cm^{-1} . Panel (c) shows the difference between residuals reported in (a) and (b).

Fig. 6: Same as figure 5 but for a tangent height of 15.9 km.

Fig. 7 : Panel (a) : average of 55 MIPAS spectra acquired during orbits 2081 and 2082 for a sub-interval of band A, at tangent altitude of 12 km. Panels (b), (c), (d) show the REC-corrected average residuals from simulations of type S1, S2 and S3, respectively (see text for details). Panel (e) shows the difference between residuals reported in (b) and (d).

Fig. 8: Same as figure 7 but for a tangent height of 24 km.

Figure 1: Measured atmospheric transmission in the region of the $\nu_5+\nu_7-\nu_7$ for an elevation angle of 2.75° (\bullet) and corresponding calculated values with (---) the old HNO_3 line list [16,18], and (—) the new improved one [17]. Plots in panels (a) and (b) are the corresponding differences between measured and calculated values. Panel (c) shows the difference between residuals reported in (a) and (b).

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